

Skills Specializing in Data Technologies in Educational Administration and Mental Education Center in Our Schools

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Abstract

Teachers may use the system to create customized survey questions and then modify the design of the mental training platform for young kids based on the input received. This iterative process aims to enhance the platform's alignment with the students' needs and preferences. One of the significant factors hindering the development of the psychological crisis early warning system in schools and universities is the absence of specialized abilities in data technologies inside the mental training center. This team necessitates a collective set of competencies that include a comprehensive understanding of both physical and mental training knowledge, with specialized expertise in the field of big data technology. By implementing a university-based mental health education center equipped with physical and mental training resources, as well as advanced data technology capabilities, we can optimize the use of data technology and address the limitations of conventional psychological early warning approaches. The utilization of big data in the realm of mental health education for university students is a novel subject matter that necessitates the involvement of proficient technological professionals and psychological specialists, and necessitates ongoing advancement and improvement. Given the existing deficiency in research and application abilities pertaining to technology inside educational institutions, it is imperative to enhance the capacity for technological development and address the obstacles associated with technology implementation by leveraging resource integration and using alternative strategies. Resource integration may be achieved via several means, including collaboration among institutions and collaboration between universities and corporations. For instance, reputable academic institutions have the capacity to undertake targeted research on the use of artificial intelligence and big data in enhancing mental health education for university students, leveraging the synergy between these two domains.

Keywords: *Educational Administration, Mental Education in Our Schools, Specialization in Data Technologies, Special Talents, Educational Sciences*

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Introduction

By fostering collaboration between technical specialists and psychological experts, it is possible to address the shortcomings of universities in technology development and implementation. This collaborative effort may result in the creation of a technologically advanced platform that effectively caters to the mental health education requirements of university students. Furthermore, the educational institution can establish collaborations with external companies or organizations that possess robust technical capabilities. By leveraging its expertise in psychology and integrating it with the technological advancements of these external entities, the institution can foster the transformation of relevant technological concepts into tangible innovations.

Simultaneously, it is important to consider the individualized aspects of students' mental well-being. Consequently, addressing the pertinent concerns necessitates not only focusing on the advancement of the initial technological platform but also ensuring consistent technical maintenance and updates, as recommended by the subsequent educational institution. The use of artificial intelligence and big data technologies may be employed to carefully monitor and align with the evolving landscape of mental health education practices among university students. For instance, educational institutions may often enhance the model inside their assessment system for college student mental health to maximize the alignment between the model and the data stored in the database. The stage of university education is a pivotal era in individuals' personal and intellectual growth. At this juncture, university students exhibit heightened sensitivity and instability, making them hesitant to broach topics pertaining to psychological concerns and crises. Schools establish a psychological crisis early warning system with the aim of providing support to pupils. Once the psychological status information of students is obtained, it is essential to prioritize the utmost security of this information and restrict the quantity of input ports for APP information.

It is essential for counselors, classroom instructors, and members of psychological boards to adhere to rigorous confidentiality protocols in order to prevent any potentially detrimental impact on pupils. This paper employs big data technology to address the limitations of conventional psychological crisis warning approaches, given the prevalent occurrence of such crises among students in the present context. The six components of psychological early warning

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data are collected, and afterwards, big data technology is used to evaluate, investigate, and forecast the aforementioned data. The mental health education center and instructors provide psychological therapies to kids based on the findings of their assessments. Simultaneously, a neural network model based on the Backpropagation (BP) algorithm is developed to forecast psychological crises. The performance of this model is then compared to that of the commonly used gray prediction model.

The findings indicate that the use of big data technology and BP neural network in a psychological crisis early warning system enables the fast and precise assessment of students' psychological status. This is achieved by leveraging the timeliness of big data technology, resulting in a remarkable prediction accuracy rate of 0.976. This demonstrates the soundness of the paradigm and underscores the need of doing research. Furthermore, taking into account the prevailing issues in the present educational administration of university students, this paper puts up six measures derived from the findings of the analysis:

- (1) Establishing a multi-level link feedback early warning system,*
- (2) Encouraging students to participate actively in the construction of psychological crisis early warning,*
- (3) Optimizing the application mode of technology,*
- (4) Developing a team of psychological talents with big data technology,*
- (5) Integrate data technology development resources and*
- (6) To ensure data security, to ensure the mental health and physical and mental safety of university students of the mental health education center.*

The evaluation of school teaching psychology management and its influence on the growth of school teaching psychology management is a crucial criterion in assessing the quality of educational psychology management within the school system. Nevertheless, the conventional educational institutions' psychological management system is encountering difficulties in fulfilling

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the innovative requirements of the contemporary talent development model in higher vocational education.

Findings

The establishment of a novel micro-level educational institution necessitates the implementation of psychological management strategies, organizational structures, procedural frameworks, and technological systems that can effectively accommodate the institution's operations at both the intermediate and macro levels. Nevertheless, Vocational Schools exhibit several discrepancies in their internal and external administrative systems. These include subpar administrative efficiency, the broad application of administrative authority, inadequate specialization in administrative psychology management, and an irrational administrative and organizational structure. This essay examines the ways in which schools are adapting their psychological management and university changes to align with the unique qualities of the digital era. This article presents the collaborative psychology management innovation network model of schools and universities, drawing upon the collaborative innovation theory in the field. This study integrates principles from psychology management theory with empirical research on collaborative innovation in educational institutions. By doing so, it broadens the scope of application and research within the field of innovation network theory. Additionally, this study develops and examines an evaluation index system for assessing students' satisfaction with the teaching of psychology management in schools.

Reading and Consulting Materials and Communicating with Teachers and Students

A questionnaire on psychological management was developed for educational purposes, with its design informed by the assessment of student satisfaction. The experimental findings indicate a significant rise in teaching satisfaction, with a growth of around 31% when compared to the period prior to the implementation of innovation and reform. The implementation of

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innovation and reform from the outset may have a significant impact, catering to the requirements of students and facilitating the enhancement of teaching psychology management quality.

In recent years, there has been an increasing focus on the investigation of internal psychological management inside vocational institutions. Nevertheless, the majority of individuals continue to be engaged in frontline roles, with little emphasis on conventional theoretical investigation (Ling et al., 2021). The aforementioned experiences exhibit a limited perspective and lack the necessary depth to fully engage with the theoretical aspects of guide practice. The author selected the study subject "Research on psychology management innovation in Vocational Schools" (Zheng et al., 2021c) due to the existing disparity between theoretical advancements and practical requirements, as well as the characteristics of the field. This article seeks to explore the implementation of internal psychology management within educational institutions, with the objective of identifying theoretical frameworks that can facilitate the sustainable development of higher professional education. By enhancing the existing theory of higher vocational education, this research aims to contribute to its effective implementation and impact. The significance of supporting the advancement of vocational education is emphasized in the scholarly work of Zheng et al. (2021a).

Vocational colleges achieve sustained growth through reintegration and allocation of high-quality social resources via the use of innovative management practices in the field of psychology (Sayaf et al., 2021). According to Li et al. (2021), this approach offers a novel framework for advancing higher vocational education, enhancing the theoretical foundations of this field, and presenting a fresh theoretical paradigm for the establishment of a contemporary university system inside China's educational institutions. In contrast to general education, higher vocational education has a stronger correlation with the market and business sectors, displaying less reliance on governmental entities, more adaptability, and an increased propensity for system innovation.

Hence, it is of significant theoretical relevance to recognize the implementation of psychology management in Vocational Schools and to develop a novel psychology management model that aligns with the contemporary university system.

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Literature Review

The ongoing progress in computer technology and the evolving understanding of learning principles are important elements that underpin the sustained growth of online education. According to Adarkwah (2021), there has been research conducted on the implementation of computer-assisted knowledge teaching platforms in the context of university education reform. Information technology is a crucial component of the broader field of information technology and plays a significant role in the process of integrating technology into education. Consequently, the instruction of knowledge has emerged as a pivotal aspect of educational reform (Zheng et al., 2021b). The imparting of knowledge via teaching has remarkable benefits and significant potential, making it a pivotal factor in enhancing the standard of education and training (Kang et al., 2022). According to Sun M, it is recommended that educators thoroughly contemplate the prudent selection and use of information within the framework of instructional design. Additionally, they should take into account the interplay between knowledge and other components of teaching in a complete and systematic manner. The study conducted by Ramírez-Montoya et al. (2021) presents a proposed design for an educational innovation process targeted towards university students pursuing a specialization in health sciences. Additionally, the document delineated some approaches that might facilitate evaluation and cooperative advancement. Presently, the educational institutions in prominent nations worldwide have established a variety of organizational frameworks, such as schools, departments, research institutes, and laboratory facilities (Wang et al., 2021a). These structures have been designed with a flexible approach to foster interdisciplinary vocational education, while also considering the evolving demands of the contemporary workforce and the global market. Developed a method aimed at facilitating the establishment of an educational framework. The present study examines the research conducted by academics in the field of psychology management, specifically focusing on the experiences and expertise of British and French higher education professionals. This research explores several aspects such as psychology management, innovation, and tolerance, as discussed in the study conducted by Zhang et al. (2022). The University of Psychology's

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administration provided clarification about the primary roles of the British and French national authorities in upholding educational standards (Li et al., 2017; Gümüş et al., 2020). In contemporary times, there exists a notable need for the acquisition of digital literacy skills and English language proficiency. According to Thorson K, several parties, including conventional news providers, personal media users, social connections, advertisers, and computer algorithms, engage in comparable "curation" processes inside personal networks. According to the studies conducted by Akhtar et al. (2020), Sarid (2021), and Huang et al. (2022), it has been found that...

Argument

The identification of rivalry, overlap, and convergence across different media streams is of paramount importance in comprehending contemporary media exposure and its influence. The technique used by the researcher introduces new definitions for study themes such as polarization, selectivity, and accidental exposure within the context of discussing participation, conceptual orientation, and computational methodologies. The endeavors of several educators and researchers in the field of education often stimulate advancements in the pedagogy of chemistry. Numerous endeavors of this kind have been documented within every sub-discipline within the field of chemistry. Nevertheless, there is a scarcity of papers documenting attempts to reproduce previously published findings (Abbas et al., 2020; Khokhar et al., 2020a,b; Irfan et al., 2022). The study conducted by Magnano et al. (2021) delves into the topic of reproducibility and replicability in scientific research, examining several challenges associated with the replication of prior studies. The ramifications of this endeavor on educators' creative teaching and learning initiatives are discussed by Goldsby et al. (2021). The central focus of Goel and Jones' (2016) perspective on educational equity for developing bilinguals is the placement of children and their actions within the social context. The study conducted by Picone et al. (2021) utilizes Ophelia's own writings and contributions from many writers, including both present and past pupils, to investigate the potential of individuals' dynamic bilingual practices in fostering innovation within the field of bilingual education theory and practice. This paper has significant theoretical and practical relevance, as well as research value. The significance of this article resides in its emphasis on the need to

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redefine the notion of management, particularly by incorporating "Humanistic" principles that prioritize the cultivation of personal inclusivity and the advancement of students' individuality, thereby optimizing their potential.

Another significant development is the introduction of advanced management tools. On one side, the prominence of research is seen in the use of research and legal remedies. National institutions play a pivotal role in shaping the education model and framework via legislative measures. They exert influence on the growth of schools by enforcing adherence to this model or framework. Additionally, these institutions adapt the professional and career environments to accommodate changing socio-economic conditions as needed. Additionally, it is crucial to effectively distribute and promote the legislation inside the educational institution, elucidate the rights and responsibilities of students, and encourage educators and learners to use legal means to safeguard their lawful rights and interests. The third aspect pertains to the advancement of management technologies. This article proposes a collaborative innovation approach between schools and universities, which may use management theory to support school management innovation and facilitate instructional change.

University Psychology Management in the Digital Age

The foundational structure of instructional psychology management innovation encompasses three levels: macro, meso, and micro (Wang et al., 2021a). The components of school psychology management innovation are intricately interrelated and mutually influential, thereby constituting the foundational framework. The field of university psychology serves as the fundamental basis for driving innovation in management practices.

The innovation process in the management of psychology in vocational schools.

During the first phase of issue identification, it is important to first identify and validate the discontent present in vocational schools. Currently, stakeholders in state higher vocational

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colleges express their dissatisfaction primarily in the following areas: students exhibit discontent towards the faculty, unemployed faculty and staff are dissatisfied with the salary system and performance appraisal system, and there is concern regarding the intervention or lack thereof from the secondary education department. The study conducted by Rashid et al. (2021) highlights many key sources of discontent, including the functional department's unhappiness, the dissatisfaction of government and enterprises about the awareness and capacity of higher vocational schools to contribute to the local economy, and the dissatisfaction with the competent departments of higher vocational schools. These factors are deemed significant in the context of the study. Next, the inspiration phase aims to generate ideas or approaches for addressing challenges inside and outside higher vocational institutions (Saloviita & Pakarinen, 2021). To address the aforementioned discontent, vocational schools should use innovative strategies in psychology management, with a primary focus on psychology management innovation. There are often two categories of technological innovations in psychology management: the implementation of established methods, processes, structures, or technologies in psychology management; and the development of novel models and approaches for psychology management, promoting self-renewal and advancement (Sarwar et al., 2018). Thirdly, during the phase of proposing and evaluating creative strategies, the inventive strategy is formulated and its viability is assessed based on the inspiration received. The utilization of advanced enterprise experience and foreign vocational education, as well as the implementation of advanced psychology management methods, processes, structures, and technologies by reputable vocational schools in our country, should not be restricted solely to the internal and external rights and interests of these educational institutions. According to Sarwar et al. (2019), in order to ensure the rapid advancement of vocational education in most vocational high schools, it is necessary for higher vocational institutions to engage in comprehensive deliberation and evaluation led by experts prior to initiating a specific creative project. This approach serves to enhance the practicality and viability of the program.

The implementation plan phase involves the actualization of the inherent value of the psychological management innovation phase (Sarwar & Khan, 2015). The assessment of benefits and losses pertaining to different interests is an essential aspect that cannot be overlooked prior to

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the complete manifestation of innovation's efficacy. Consequently, the implementation process of psychological management innovation is often impeded (Sarwar et al., 2022). Hence, it is imperative for vocational schools to receive support from both internal and external guiding forces when implementing substantial innovations. This support is primarily manifested through two key aspects: firstly, the establishment of a specialized organization for managing innovative practices in psychology, which is led and operated by the school's principal. The second approach entails effectively organizing and promoting the collective efforts of academics and staff, while using staff organization as a means to address real-world challenges (Farooq et al., 2019; Waheed et al., 2020; Sarwar et al., 2022). In the fifth step, the process of conceptualizing, defining, and distributing plays a crucial role in attributing significance to and validating the implementation of innovative practices in the field of psychological management. The primary objective of this invention is to describe the experience of effectively executing psychological management innovation and identify any patterns or regularities that might provide guidance for future practice.

Collaborative innovation entities inside the collaborative innovation network of educational institutions foster the development of trust, reciprocity, recognition, and other forms of organizational connections via their exchanges and interactions. According to Firmansyah et al. (2020), the attainment of the collaborative innovation objective at educational institutions may be facilitated by the establishment of an enhanced collaborative partnership. For instance, educational institutions that foster stronger "interpersonal connections" exhibit a heightened level of confidence among partners engaged in collaborative innovation. This inclination towards establishing more robust and enduring collaborations leads to a systematic reduction in the costs and risks associated with collaborative endeavors, ultimately enhancing the likelihood of successful outcomes (Jia, 2021). A higher degree of interpersonal connection is more likely to foster subsequent collaborative endeavors. Hence, the stakeholders involved in the joint innovation efforts between schools and universities demonstrate active dedication towards fostering an enhanced "relationship".

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Analysis of Corporate Behavior and Goals

Businesses have a vital role in assessing the worth of innovative accomplishments. The realization of genuine innovation necessitates the transformation of technical items into commodities. Enterprises choose for university collaborative innovation as a strategic approach to attain success in market competitiveness and ensure sustainable growth. The objective of optimization is to continuously engage in research and development endeavors aimed at minimizing production expenses and maximizing financial gains. Hence, it is essential for collaborations between universities and industries in the realm of innovation to be guided by market forces. This entails establishing a harmonious equilibrium between the supply of research outcomes from the laboratory and the demand for these outcomes in the market, achieved via institutional linkages. The collaborative innovation mode between schools is perceived as a strategic and systematic project that encompasses the planning of diverse advantages, the exploration of internal advantages through theoretical frameworks, and the practical application of interdisciplinary combinations. This mode involves the engagement of external business teams, technology, and knowledge, all facilitated through collaborative efforts. It is essential to address the requirements of innovation platforms or collaborative initiatives, facilitate the development of competent engineering and technical professionals, and cater to the demands of synchronized innovation. The propensity and vigor of firms of different sizes to participate in joint research and development activities exhibit variations. Research has shown that organizations with greater size and enhanced economic and technical capabilities exhibit a higher level of enthusiasm for collaborative innovation. However, the level of desire to cooperate among small and medium-sized firms is sometimes uncertain prior to their decision to engage in collaborations with other businesses, research institutions, or colleges.

Based on empirical evidence derived from surveys and research, it has been shown that some organizations that have a propensity for engaging in collaborative innovation often exhibit the following discernible characteristics: The firm operates within an industry characterized by a significant presence of scientific and technological advancements, and is subject to intense rivalry from industry peers. As a result, the firm has a greater inclination to engage in joint research and development endeavors with other companies due to the prevailing environmental conditions.

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Another aspect is that in the event of internal organizational issues, there is a need and willingness to seek assistance from external research and development (R&D) teams. There are many justifications for organizations to participate in collaborative innovation. One such reason is the ability to include external resources that are of higher quality, which may enhance the overall innovation process. Additionally, collaborative innovation allows for the sharing of benefits among participating entities, fostering a sense of mutual gain. Furthermore, the synergistic production resulting from collaboration can lead to amplified advantages and improved outcomes. The use of more advanced capabilities and technological items inside a business may eventually lead to increased profitability and reduced manufacturing costs. Within the context of inter-enterprise collaboration, industrial organizations that serve as implementers and promoters of scientific and technological products undertake the task of evaluating the alignment of research and development outcomes with market demands. They also facilitate the process of transforming these outcomes into commercially viable products, while conducting thorough investigations and documentation of any identified defects or shortcomings. The advent of new technical goods has facilitated the establishment of a real-time feedback loop, hence enhancing the viability of joint innovation research and development endeavors inside academic institutions.

The optimization of the advantageous outcomes derived from the joint innovation efforts inside the organization. In the research and development (R&D) process, corporations are required to provide resources not only for project funding, but also for capital investment, staff acquisition, procurement of technical equipment, and acquisition of expertise, among other essential components. Additionally, it is expected to provide assistance in the realm of financial investments. The kinds and amounts of creative resources have a direct impact on the financial expenses incurred by the organization. The increase in expenses may also be attributed to factors such as the amount of inter-organizational relationships within cooperative organizations, the degree of homogeneity across firms, and intense market rivalry. Hence, it is essential for firms to allocate a portion of their budget towards the establishment and sustenance of collaborative relationships (Jin, 2022). There is a positive correlation between the degree of connection and the speed of establishing collaborative partnerships, as well as the efficacy of creative products. This link contributes to the sustained and steady growth of collaborative innovation inside institutions. at

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the context of collaborative innovation at educational institutions, the primary source of financial resources is derived from the sale of novel goods or patents. *This is driven by the profit maximization objective of business entities engaged in collaborative innovation. Due to the global impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, a significant number of institutions worldwide have transitioned to the e-learning format. Consequently, this shift has introduced novel variables such as academic involvement, which have begun to have an influence on students' academic performance.* Psychological security is considered to be one of the contributing aspects in this context.

Numerous scholarly investigations have been conducted to explore the significance of psychological safety levels among students. Within this body of research, several scholars have proposed a specific approach for evaluating this particular indicator. Nevertheless, there is a paucity of research examining the correlation between students' degrees of psychological stability and their dedication and success in academic settings. The objective of the current investigation is to address this existing knowledge deficit.

The study included online questionnaires as a means of investigating the psychological safety levels, academic involvement, and performance of students in the e-learning process. Additionally, the study aimed to investigate the potential links that exist between these factors. The female participants exhibited a greater degree of psychological safety while expressing their own thoughts, particularly within the context of webinar environments. Similar patterns were seen in both academic dedication and degrees of achievement. The results derived from using the linear regression analysis method indicated a favorable relationship between psychological security and academic success. In contrast to prior research, the concept of student security is now being recognized not just as a facet of personal data security, but likewise as a psychological factor. It may be inferred that the impact of psychological safety on students' engagement and academic achievement is particularly prominent within the context of online education. The purpose of this section is to provide an overview of the topic at hand. In light of the circumstances surrounding the COVID-19 pandemic in March 2020, the city of St. Petersburg, Russia, implemented measures in accordance with the guidance provided by health authorities. The majority of institutions

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worldwide, including St. Petersburg Polytechnic University (SPbPU), have transitioned to the e-learning style. The existing situation necessitated immediate modifications, since the proportion of online university courses was just 4%, partly online courses accounted for 14%, and the majority, 82%, were conducted in a full-time format (Authors and Khalyapina, 2019; Authors, 2020).

The whole shift towards digital learning has presented several challenges across all domains of education (Authors & Khalyapina, 2019). Buzzetto-More and Koohang (2009) as well as Jorge Miguel Moneo et al. (2015) have identified many areas that are impacted by the phenomenon under consideration. These areas include the psychological well-being of both students and instructors, the level of student involvement, and, of equal significance, academic achievement. Numerous scholars have conducted investigations on diverse indicators that possess the potential to have a direct or indirect influence on students' attitudes towards the educational process, as well as their academic involvement and performance (Miguel Moneo et al., 2015). Ensuring students' psychological safety is a crucial aspect of the university's role in transitioning to e-learning.

Conclusion

This study provides a significant addition to the existing literature by conducting a complete assessment of university students' psychological security, academic commitment, and performance. It aims to investigate the potential impact of psychological security on academic commitment and performance by analyzing the views of university students. In order to effectively establish an educational environment that promotes positive outcomes, the following study topics are proposed:

- 1. Is there a big difference in the levels of psychological safety, academic commitment, and academic performance between men and women?*
- 2. How do students' varying degrees of psychological security relate to their behavioral, emotional, and cognitive commitments?*

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3. *How do students' different degrees of psychological security relate to their academic performance?*
4. *To what extent does the level of psychological safety predict students' academic performance and participation?*

Therefore, this study pursues the following as key objectives:

- a) *to determine the relationships between psychological safety, academic commitment, academic performance and gender in a sample of university students;*
- b) *to establish the relationships between psychological security level, academic commitment and performance.*

Theoretical Framework of E-Learning E-learning is widely recognized as a novel educational methodology that incorporates many forms of technology-supported learning and teaching methods (Tavangarian et al., 2004). It comprises a range of definitions aimed at enhancing access to educational materials, promoting learner flexibility, and expanding cognitive capabilities (Lowenthal et al., 2009). Additionally, this method is often regarded as the most efficient and economically viable approach, making it accessible to individuals from all socioeconomic backgrounds to engage in the educational endeavor. According to Nazarova (2018), the concept of Dynamic e-Learning pertains to the provision of creative information that is readily available to all pupils. The use of e-learning technology provides educational institutions with many benefits, such as a concise and effective learning process, adaptability, and modular structure. One of the limitations associated with e-learning is the prevalence of high dropout rates, as well as the substantial expenditures associated with designing and maintaining e-learning platforms (Iacob, 2011).

Frisby R. User involvement in mental health branch education: client review presentations. *Nurse Education Today*. 2001;21(8):663–669. doi: 10.1054/nedt.2001.0669.

Full Text | Google Scholar Irfan, M., Shahid, AL, Ahmad, M., Iqbal, W., Elavarasan, RM, Ren, S., et al. (2022). Assessment of public intention to get vaccination against COVID-19: evidence from a developing country. *J Eval. Clin. practice* 28, 63–73. doi: 10.1111/jep.13611

Goel, S., and Jones, RJ (2016). Entrepreneurial exploration and exploitation in family business: a systematic review and future directions. *fam. bus. Rev.* 29, 94–120. doi: 10.1177/0894486515625541

Goldsby, MG, Goldsby, EA, Neck, CB, et al. (2021). Self-leadership: a four decade review of the literature and trainings. *adm. sci.* 11:25. doi: 10.3390/ADMSCI11010025

Gümüş, S., Arar, K., and Oplatka, I. (2020). Review of international research on school leadership for social justice, equity and diversity 53, 81–99. doi: 10.1080/00220620.2020.1862767,

Huang, X., Chau, KY, Tang, YM, and Iqbal, W. (2022). Business ethics and irrationality in SME during COVID-19: does it impact on sustainable business resilience? *front. environ. sci.* 10:870476. doi: 10.3389/FENVS.2022.870476

Jia, H. (2021). EFL Learners' well-being and their academic engagement: the mediating role of EFL Learners' self-efficacy. *front. Psychol.* 3:882886.

Jin, Y. (2022). Analysis of college Students' entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial psychological quality from the perspective of ideology and political education. *front. Psychol.* 13:739353. doi: 10.3389/FPSYG.2022.739353

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Kang, N., Bell, S., Ward Thompson, C., Zheng, M., Xu, Z., and Sun, Z. (2022). Use of urban residential community parks for stress management during the COVID-19 lockdown period in China. *front. Psychol.* 13:816417. doi: 10.3389/FPSYG.2022.816417

Khokhar, M., Hou, Y., Rafique, MA, and Iqbal, W. (2020a). Evaluating the social sustainability criteria of supply chain management in manufacturing industries: a role of BWM in MCDM. *probl. Ekorozwoju* 15, 185–194. doi: 10.35784/pe.2020.2.18

Khokhar, M., Iqbal, W., Hou, Y., Abbas, M., and Fatima, A. (2020b). Assessing supply chain performance from the perspective of pakistan's manufacturing industry through social sustainability. *PRO* 8:1064. doi: 10.3390/pr8091064

Khoo R., Mcvicar A., Brandon D. Service user involvement in postgraduate mental health education. Does it benefit practice? *Journal of Mental Health.* 2004;13(5):481–492. doi: 10.1080/09638230400006742.

Li, J., Xu, K., Chaudhuri, S., Yumer, E., Zhang, H., and Guibas, L. (2017). GRASS: generative recursive autoencoders for shape structures. *ACM Trans. graph.* 36, 1–14. doi: 10.1145/3072959.3073637

Li, Y., Nishimura, N., Yagami, H., and Park, HS (2021). An empirical study on online learners' continuance intentions in China. *Sustainability* 13:889. doi: 10.3390/SU13020889

Ling, Y., Jeong, SJ, and Wang, L. (2021). Research on the reform of management system of higher vocational education in China based on personality standard. *Curr. Psychol.* doi: 10.1007/S12144-021-01480-6

Magnano, P., Lodi, E., Zammitti, A., and Patrizi, P. (2021). Courage, career adaptability, and readiness as resources to improve well-being during the university-to-work transition in Italy. *int. J. Environ. pic. Public Health* 18:2919. doi: 10.3390/IJERPH18062919

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Picone, PM, De Massis, A., Tang, Y., and Piccolo, RF (2021). The psychological foundations of management in family: values, biases, firms and heuristics. *fam. bus. Rev.* 34, 12–32. doi: 10.1177/0894486520985630

Quick JC, American Psychological Association/National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health, Health Promotion Panel, 1990 Work and Well-Being Conference Occupational mental health promotion: a prevention agenda based on education and treatment. *American Journal of Health Promotion.* 1992;7(1):37–44. doi: 10.4278/0890-1171-7.1.37.

Ramírez-Montoya, MS, Loaiza-Aguirre, MI, Zúñiga-Ojeda, A., and Portuguese-Castro, M. (2021). Characterization of the teaching profile within the framework of education 4.0. *Future Internet* 13:91. doi: 10.3390/FI13040091

Rashid, AS, Tout, K., and Yakan, A. (2021). The critical human behavior factors and their impact on knowledge management system–cycles. *bus. Process. manag. J.* 27, 1677–1702. doi: 10.1108/BPMJ-11-2020-0508

Sharp W., Hargrove DS, Johnson L., Deal WP Mental health education: an evaluation of a classroom based strategy to modify help seeking for mental health problems. *Journal of College Student Development.* 2006;47(4):419–438. doi: 10.1353/csd.2006.0051.